

100% of the world's vulnerable communities to be tsunami ready by 2030 - really?

Discussion Paper - A brief interjection from the sideline by Harald Spahn,

Freelance Consultant, Apen, Germany

Ensuring that 100% of the world's tsunami-prone communities meet the IOC-UNESCO Tsunami Ready Programme indicators by 2030, as outlined in the UN Ocean Decade Tsunami Programme (ODTP), is certainly an ambitious and worthy goal, but is it really achievable, especially when we consider the scale of the challenge and the progress so far to strengthen community preparedness? We are talking here about many hundreds of districts, cities and villages alone in Indonesia that face tsunami threats.

As practitioner involved over many years in tsunami preparedness projects and activities in the Indian Ocean region, I want to share my thoughts on this with a wider audience. It is not about questioning the goal, even if it does not seem very realistic to me, but rather about pointing out, based on practical experience, some of the important requirements that I believe are necessary in order to move this important process forward.

Overall, it seems that the focus is currently still very much on promoting and implementing the "Tsunami Ready Recognition Program" (TRRP) that sets up structures and mechanisms in the participating countries to assess the "achievement" of a set of 12 indicators and to award certificates to those communities that have managed to do so. Concerning for me is that a lot of energy goes into a verification and certification process, which will tie up resources in the long term as the number of certificates is expected to increase significantly in the future and will also have to be renewed at regular intervals. So far, Tsunami Ready training courses by the Ocean Teacher Global Academy (OTGA) or the Tsunami Information Centers (TICs) mainly focus on the concept, process and indicators of the Recognition Program.

Need for a "Tsunami Ready Community Support Program"

What I do not see yet, is an initiative that provides the necessary support and resources on a wider scale, let's call it a "Tsunami Ready Community Support Program", to raise awareness and interest among vulnerable communities and then accompany them on their way to building local tsunami preparedness.

My experiences teaches me that this kind of support is essential to strengthen community preparedness. Communities will always be facing regulatory, procedural and technical issues for which they need expert advice, and there is usually a need for practical guidance on how to plan and set up local preparedness and response processes. So far, such support has been provided selectively through different kind of projects and collaborative efforts, but is not yet available on a larger scale.

Community ownership and understanding local tsunami risk are key prerequisites

Another essential prerequisite for effective and sustainable community preparedness and response capacity is local ownership. In my experience, this is perhaps the most important factor. I agree, as set out in the ODTP Research, Development and Implementation Plan, that risk perception can be an important driver for mobilising people and resources for awareness and preparedness. Providing risk information and discussing it with communities at risk could therefore be a good starting point for triggering locally led preparedness initiatives.

However, the reality is, that most communities still lack locally tailored hazard and risk information. And although simple but robust approaches are available and there is a lot of capacity and expertise in the academic community for tsunami modelling, we have not yet managed to provide all threatened communities with adequate inundation maps at local scale. This is critical, as a solid understanding of the hazard and the potential impact in terms of inundation is an essential foundation for any meaningful local tsunami preparedness initiatives.

Technical guidance, process facilitation and small funds are on demand

Experiences show that the communities usually demand three types of support: (1) technical guidance, (2) access to skilled facilitators to help them navigate the planning and establishment of local preparedness and response processes, and quite often (3) access to small funds that can be used for initial activities, such as initial public awareness campaigns and exercises, or the installation of signage, for which local budget has not yet been allocated.

Given the scale of the challenge, the importance of local ownership, and the need to support a very large number of vulnerable communities, what are the ingredients for an effective support mechanism? In principle, such support must work on a larger scale, be easily accessible and affordable. And it should be demand-driven, meaning that communities should be able to apply for it as soon as they have decided to make themselves tsunami ready.

Providing such support to communities is, of course, in the first instance a national responsibility and task. However, well-designed and coordinated cooperation between the international community and interested countries could be the way to achieve this on a larger scale while keeping it affordable.

Knowledge resource platforms could play a crucial role in providing technical and process guidance to assist communities. For many of the issues that a community will encounter on its way to tsunami

preparedness, there are already IOC Manuals and Guidelines available to support the implementation. Topics include inundation modelling and mapping, evacuation mapping, response and evacuation planning, and tsunami exercises. Practical, hands-on guides with country-specific information and references as well as translations into relevant local languages should complement these. The development of such platforms could be facilitated through well-coordinated cooperation between national and international players, in which the TICs could play a guiding and coordinating role.

With such resource platforms behind them, countries could focus on implementing national programmes to raise awareness, motivate communities to act and support them throughout the process on demand. Key to this is the human element, as it requires skilled facilitators who are available to engage with the communities. Group approaches can come into play here, as well as peer group learning and direct exchange of experiences between communities but also making use of digital media, which these days offer many innovative options to achieve a greater reach and impact.

Think big - it will take good ideas, adequate funding and international cooperation

All of this requires good concepts and, of course, adequate resources. This will not be possible without national funding, but international cooperation and public-private partnership can also play their part. The initiative of the Working Group on Tsunamis and Other Hazards related to Sea Level Warning and Mitigation Systems (TOWS) to establish a *Tsunami Ready Coalition*, involving key stakeholders across the UN structure as well as national disaster management agencies, could play a critical role in making a “Tsunami Ready Community Support Programme” a reality.

Does this sound too ambitious? Perhaps, but without thinking big and scaling up, the ultimate goal of making communities worldwide tsunami-ready is unlikely to be achieved.

References

GITEWS/PROTECTS (2013): *Our Experiences: Tsunami Preparedness in Local Communities - A Structured Approach for Capacity Development*. Tsunami-Kit [https://www.gitews.de/tsunami-kit/en/E6/our_experience/Tsunami Preparedness in Local Communities.pdf](https://www.gitews.de/tsunami-kit/en/E6/our_experience/Tsunami%20Preparedness%20in%20Local%20Communities.pdf) (last visited on 27 July 2025)

Spahn, H., Hoppe, M., Kodijat, A., Rafliana, I., Usdianto, B., Vidiarina, H.D. (2014): *Walking the Last Mile: Contributions to the Development of an End-to-End Tsunami Early Warning System in Indonesia*. In: Wenzel, F., Zschau, J. (eds) *Early Warning for Geological Disasters. Advanced Technologies in Earth Sciences*. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-12233-0_10

UNESCO/IOC (2022): *Standard Guidelines for the Tsunami Ready Recognition Programme*. IOC Manuals and Guides No74. Paris, UNESCO

UNESCO/IOC (2023): *Research, Development and Implementation Plan for the Ocean Decade Tsunami Programme*. IOC Technical Series No 180. Paris, UNESCO

UNESCO/IOC (2025): *Proposed Implementation Plan for the Tsunami Ready Coalition*. Version February 2025, <https://oceanexpert.org/document/35635>